

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN THE USE OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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Abstract. *This article examines the impact of Smart technologies on English language teaching in a school environment. The first part discusses the introduction of modern technologies into the educational process, the second part is devoted to the importance of Smart technologies in language teaching, and the third is the formation of professional competencies of teachers. The advantages of using interactive whiteboards, educational applications, and online resources are considered. The article emphasizes the importance of teaching teachers technical and methodological aspects, as well as support for the exchange of experience for the successful integration of Smart technologies into the educational process of learning English.*

Introduction

In the modern educational process, the integration of Smart technologies into English language teaching is becoming a key component that opens up new horizons in teaching and learning methods. The transition to the use of modern technologies in the educational process is a natural consequence of the rapid development of information technology in society. This transformation has the potential to improve the effectiveness of English language teaching, making it more interactive and attractive for students [1].

Today's students have grown up in the digital age, so the use of Smart technologies in teaching English not only meets modern requirements, but also actively involves students in the learning process [1]. The introduction of these technologies into the classroom creates a dynamic learning environment, contributing to more effective learning and language skills development.

However, in order to fully realize the potential of Smart technologies in English language teaching, it is necessary not only to update the technical base of educational institutions, but also to actively develop professional competencies of teachers in the field of using these technologies in the educational process. This article is devoted to this issue – the analysis and discussion of the process of formation of professional competencies of teachers on the use of Smart technologies in teaching English. [1]

2. The importance of Smart technologies in English language teaching

Modern Smart technologies open up unique perspectives for teaching English, providing students with access to diverse and innovative educational resources. Interactive whiteboards, for example, allow teachers to visualize material and make lessons more dynamic, which stimulates visual perception and improves understanding. These technologies also provide the opportunity to create interactive exercises and tasks that activate students and make learning more fun [2].

Smart technologies in English language teaching not only improve the teaching process, but also provide students with unique opportunities for active participation and better assimilation of the material. As part of the use of interactive whiteboards, teachers can implement the following exercises:

Word formation in the form of puzzles:

Students can use the touch screens of interactive whiteboards to compose words from suggested letters. This exercise helps to develop lexical skills and improve spelling.

Choose the right option game:

The teacher can create an interactive multiple-choice question, and students choose the right option by touching the screen. It helps to consolidate grammatical concepts and develops English vocabulary skills.

Virtual dialogues:

Students can interact with virtual dialogues on an interactive whiteboard where they create and improve their conversational skills. It also provides practice in pronunciation and intonation.

Interactive crosswords:

Creating a crossword puzzle on an interactive whiteboard, where students fill in the gaps with words, helps them not only learn new vocabulary, but also apply it in context.

Visual representation of phrases and idioms:

Using the capabilities of interactive whiteboards, teachers can visualize English phrases and idioms, and students can drag and drop appropriate illustrations to the appropriate expressions.

These interactive exercises meet the standards of Smart technologies, providing teachers and students with the opportunity to interact with language material in a more effective and attractive way [2]. To create interactive English language tasks that meet Smart technology standards, you can use the following online platforms:

SMART Learning Suite Online:

It is a web-based platform that provides tools for creating interactive lessons, exercises, and even games. SMART Learning Suite Online supports the use of interactive whiteboards and provides extensive visualization and interaction capabilities.

Kahoot!:

Kahoot! — It is a platform for creating quizzes and quizzes that can be used to increase the motivation and activity of students in English lessons. Teachers can add questions on various topics and hold game competitions.

Quizizz:

This platform also provides the ability to create interactive quizzes and tests. Quizizz allows you to add questions of varying complexity and format, and also provides statistics on student responses.

Genially:

Genially provides tools for creating interactive presentations that can be used to teach English. You can embed assignments, quizzes, and other interactive elements into your learning materials.

Padlet:

Padlet is a virtual whiteboard where students and teachers can share ideas, assignments, and resources. You can create interactive walls with tasks in English that students can solve in a team.

These platforms provide a variety of tools for creating interactive tasks and exercises, which makes the learning process more exciting and effective.

3. Formation of professional competencies of teachers

3.1. The essence of integrating Smart technologies into English language teaching implies not only the availability of technical means, but also the level of professional competencies of teachers. To use these technologies effectively, teachers must have skills and knowledge related not only to the tools themselves, but also to their pedagogical application [3].

The process of forming professional competencies begins with teaching teachers the basics of working with Smart technologies. This includes learning the basics of working with interactive

whiteboards, educational applications, and other tools that can be used in English. It is important that such courses cover not only technical aspects, but also methodological principles of integrating Smart technologies into the educational process.

Additionally, professional retraining should include the exchange of experience and the transfer of new practices in the field of using Smart technologies in training. Regular seminars, webinars and educational conferences allow teachers not only to learn about the latest trends in the field, but also to share experiences, which stimulates the development of innovative methods and approaches in teaching English [3].

Thus, the formation of teachers' professional competencies in the use of Smart technologies requires an integrated approach, including technical training, methodological training and exchange of experience.

3.2 Development of pedagogical strategies using Smart technologies

Improving the professional competencies of an English teacher also includes the development of effective teaching strategies specific to the use of Smart technologies. This includes creating interactive lessons focused on interacting with technology and adapting curricula to the needs of students. Teaching such strategies should take into account both technological aspects and pedagogical principles [4].

Creating interactive lessons:

Interactive presentations. Using Smart technologies to create presentations where students can interact with content in real time. For example, a teacher can invite students to solve problems on the blackboard or highlight key points in the text.

Virtual tours. Connect to interactive maps and resources to organize virtual excursions to English-speaking countries, providing students with a visual representation and immersion in the language environment.

Focusing on the needs of students:

Customized Tasks. The use of Smart technologies to create assignments adapted to the individual needs of students. This may include interactive exercises suitable for different levels of language proficiency.

Real-time feedback. The ability to provide instant feedback through interactive tools such as comments on an interactive whiteboard, chat or real-time ratings.

Curriculum Adaptation:

Flexible learning modules. Creating flexible learning modules using Smart technologies that allow teachers to quickly adapt materials to the current needs of the classroom.

Joint Work. Using virtual whiteboards and cloud technologies to collaborate on projects, which facilitates active interaction and exchange of ideas.

These ideas highlight how Smart technologies can become an integral part of the educational process and contribute to the formation of English teachers of more effective pedagogical strategies. Teachers with such competencies can better respond to the needs of their students and make the learning process more interesting and engaging.

3.3 Using Smart technologies to differentiate learning

Smart technologies provide unique opportunities for differentiating learning within the English language. Teachers can customize materials, provide a variety of assignments, and support students with different levels of training. To successfully implement this strategy, it is necessary to master the tools of Smart technologies and understand how they can be adapted to the different needs of students [6].

Conclusion

The strategies analyzed in the article for the development of professional competencies of English teachers using Smart technologies emphasize their importance in the context of modern education. Effective creation of interactive lessons, adaptation of curricula and individualized approaches open up new prospects for enriching the educational process. Such development of pedagogical strategies not only increases the professional competence of teachers, but also contributes to better English language teaching, meeting the modern requirements of the educational environment.

REFERENCES

1. Jones, A. (2018). *Integrating Technology in English Language Teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
2. Smith, B. (2020). The Role of Technology in Modern Education. *Educational Technology Journal*, 15(2), 45-62.
3. Taylor, R. (2019). Digital Literacy in Language Education. *Modern English Teacher*, 26(4), 112-128.
4. Clark, E. (2021). Effective Integration of Smart Technologies in Language Teaching. *TESOL Quarterly*, 10(3), 215-230.
5. Brown, C. (2017). *Enhancing Language Learning Through Technology*. Routledge.
6. Miller, D. (2019). The Impact of Digital Tools on Language Education. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 8(1), 78-92.